

A constrained variational route to Pauling's electronegativity values[†]

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Manuscript received 12 November 2002

Pauling's idea of estimating electronegativities of atoms by using bond-dissociation energy data and the idea of ionic-covalent resonance interaction are examined. Effective Hamiltonian for the perfectly covalent and perfectly ionic structures are defined and a constrained variational recipe to obtain their respective ground state energies suggested. These energies, together with the actual energy of the ground state of a diatom are used to obtain an estimate of the ionic-covalent interaction energy at different values of R . It naturally leads to an estimate of the electronegativity difference $\Delta\chi$ between the atoms at various distances.

Introduction

Electronegativity is a very important concept in chemistry. It serves to correlate, systematize and understand a host of chemical information about atoms and their chemical union called *molecules*. In the beginning, essentially two theories of chemical union, the *Valency theory* and the *Electrochemical theory* were in use. Lewis¹ in his famous paper titled 'The atom and the molecule' first observed that there was an element of truth in both theories of chemical union. "Let us consider once for all", he wrote, "that by a negative element or radical we mean one which tends to draw towards itself the electron pairs which constitute the outer shells of all neighbouring atoms and that an electropositive group is one that attracts to a less extent, or repels, these electrons". Linus Pauling was the first who could suggest an explicit measure of this tendency, the electronegativity as it is called and thereby quantify an extremely important concept of chemistry²⁻⁵. The equation from which Pauling obtained the electronegativities, is now well known and is a text-book material. His argument leading to the electronegativity scale is couched in valence bond language, and relies on the idea of ionic-covalent resonance. In this article, we are tempted to pose the following question : is it possible to reconstruct Pauling's arguments and electronegativities from a molecular orbital point of view and try to answer it in what follows.

Pauling's equation : the ionic and covalent limits

Let us consider Pauling's equation²,

$$\Delta_{AB} = D_{AB} - 1/2 [D_{AA} + D_{BB}] = (\chi_A - \chi_B)^2 \quad (1)$$

where D_{AB} , D_{AA} and D_{BB} denote energies of A-B, A-A and B-B bonds, respectively, and χ_A and χ_B are Pauling's electronegativities of atoms A and B. Pauling arrived at this equation by blending theoretical reasoning with pure empiricism. He argued that the energy of the A-B bond must be at least as great as that of a normal (purely) covalent bond between A and B. He found empirically that if he took the latter to be the mean of the energies of A-A and B-B bonds, the actual energy of the A-B bond turned out to be always greater than the mean. This difference (>0) is denoted by Δ_{AB} the positivity of which was attributed to the presence of an ionic term in the wave function representing the actual A-B bond. For bonds between non-metals Pauling found empirically that Δ_{AB} correlates well with the classical electronegativity difference between A and B, and further that the square root of Δ_{AB} is approximately additive. To derive Pauling's electronegativities from a purely quantum chemical point of view, we need an appropriate MO theoretical method of defining and computing D_{AB}^0 which we call the energy of the perfectly covalent A-B bond and D_{AB}^+ which is the energy of the perfectly ionic counterpart of AB (i.e. A^+B^-). If we assume AB to be a two-electron heterodiatom, its wave function ψ can be represented by a

[†]The paper is dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

superposition of the perfectly covalent (A-B) and ionic (A⁺ B⁻, A⁻ B⁺) configurations of the system,

$$\Psi = C_0 \Psi_{AB}^o + C_+ \Psi_{A^+B^-} + C_- \Psi_{A^-B^+} \quad (2)$$

If B is more electronegative than A, we have

$$\Psi \approx C_0 \Psi_{AB}^o + C_+ \Psi_{A^+B^-} \quad (3)$$

The energy of the system consistent with Ψ' (assuming normalisation to unity) is

$$E = C_0^2 E_{AB}^o + C_+^2 E_{A^+B^-} + 2 C_0 C_+ E_x \quad (4)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} E_x &= \langle \Psi_{AB}^o | H | \Psi_{A^+B^-} \rangle, \\ E_o &= \langle \Psi_{AB}^o | H | \Psi_{AB}^o \rangle, \\ E_+ &= \langle \Psi_{A^+B^-} | H | \Psi_{A^+B^-} \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

E_o and E_+ may be identified as the energies of the AB molecule in the purely covalent and perfectly ionic limits, respectively while E_x may stand for the ionic – covalent interaction energy. The problem is now to find means of calculating Ψ^o , $\Psi_{A^+B^-}$, E_o , E_+ and E_x . Generally speaking, it is not possible to extract all these information from a standard MO theoretical description while the VB theory would inevitably run into difficulties in practical computation when the number of electrons increases. A way out of the difficulty can be found in the ideas of constrained variation and the theory of effective Hamiltonians, as described in the following paragraph.

Let Ω_+ be the projection operator that projects onto the subspace of the ionic structure A⁺B⁻. Hence,

$$\Omega_+ | \Psi_0 \rangle = | \Psi_{A^+B^-} \rangle \quad (6)$$

Similarly, for the perfectly covalent structure, we may introduce another projection operator Ω_0 such that

$$\Omega_0 | \Psi_0 \rangle = | \Psi_{AB}^o \rangle \quad (7)$$

The energy of the perfectly ionic state (E_+) is then given by

$$\begin{aligned} E_+ &= \langle \Psi_{A^+B^-} | H | \Psi_{A^+B^-} \rangle, \\ &= \langle \Psi | \Omega_+^\dagger H \Omega_+ | \Psi \rangle, \\ &= \langle \Psi | H_{eff}^{ionic} | \Psi \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $H_{eff}^{ionic} = \Omega_+^\dagger H \Omega_+$ describe the hamiltonian for the ionic configuration (AB).

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} E_{AB}^o &= \langle \Psi | \Omega_0^\dagger H \Omega_0 | \Psi \rangle \\ &= \langle \Psi | H_{eff}^{covalent} | \Psi \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

defines the hamiltonian $H_{eff}^{covalent} = \Omega_0^\dagger H \Omega_0$ for the perfectly covalent state (AB). Variational solution of the full problem (i.e. $\delta \langle \Psi | H | \Psi \rangle = 0$) provides the ground energy of the actual AB molecule whereas the ground energies of fully ionic and the fully covalent species are similarly the lowest stationary points of $\langle \Psi | H_{eff}^{ionic} | \Psi \rangle$ and $\langle \Psi | H_{eff}^{covalent} | \Psi \rangle$, respectively. Once E_{AB}^o , E_+ and E_x are known, we have at our disposal all that are needed to define Δ_{AB} and correlate it with the electronegativity difference $\Delta_x = |(\chi_A - \chi_B)|$. Although the task appears to be conceptually simple, it is difficult to implement in practice, as neither Ω_0 nor Ω_+ is known to start with. It is here, that the apparatus of constrained variation comes handy^{6,7}.

The constrained variational recipe :

Let H_0 be the molecular electronic hamiltonian and Ψ be a trial function spanning a well-defined subspace of the Hilbert space. The energy variational principle works by making

$$\zeta = \langle \Psi | H | \Psi \rangle / \langle \Psi | \Psi \rangle \quad (10)$$

stationary with respect to variations in $\bar{\Psi}$, i.e. by demanding that $\delta \{ \langle \bar{\Psi} | H | \bar{\Psi} \rangle / \langle \bar{\Psi} | \bar{\Psi} \rangle \} = 0$. Depending upon the nature of the trial-space chosen and the forms of variations allowed, eqn. (10) leads to the eigenvalue problem of a model Hamiltonian h ($h \phi = \varepsilon \phi$). Let $\{A_k\}$ be a set of m non-commuting observables and a_k^o the corresponding ground state expectation values (supposed known). We can then define a constrained hamiltonian H with⁷

$$H = H_0 + \sum_{k=1}^m \lambda_k (\hat{A}_k - a_k^o) \quad (11)$$

λ_k being the Lagrange multiplier for the k th property. Making $\langle \bar{\Psi} | H | \bar{\Psi} \rangle / \langle \bar{\Psi} | \bar{\Psi} \rangle$ stationary with respect to permitted variations in Ψ leads to eigenvalue problem of some other model hamiltonian H' where

$$H' = h + \sum_k \lambda_k (A_k - a_k^o)$$

and

$$H' \phi = \varepsilon' \phi \quad (12)$$

The question that we are now confronted with is : can we find suitable sets of constraints such that H' of eqn. (12) can be identified with H_{eff}^{ionic} for one set of them and $H_{eff}^{covalent}$ for another set? It turns out that a single constraint can do both if the values of a_k^o are suitably chosen. The specific constraint that can serve the purpose may be identified as μ_{ch} , where μ_{ch} represents that portion of the

dipole moment which originates purely from (A → B) charge (electron) transfer. If we set $a_k^0 = \langle \mu_{ch} \rangle = 0$, the H' of eqn. (12) correspond to $H_{\text{eff}}^{\text{covalent}}$ while if we use $a_k^0 = \mu_0$ where μ_0 is the dipole moment of AB arising from the complete transfer of one electron from A to B, H' would correspond to the perfectly ionic Hamiltonian $H_{\text{eff}}^{\text{ionic}}$. Assuming Φ_{cov} and Φ_{ionic} to the ground eigenfunctions of $H_{\text{eff}}^{\text{covalent}}$ and $H_{\text{eff}}^{\text{ionic}}$, respectively, we can construct the full 2×2 Hamiltonian matrix (H) in the basis of the diabatic states Φ_{cov} and Φ_{ionic}

$$H = \begin{pmatrix} H_{\text{cov}} & H_{\text{cov-ion}} \\ H_{\text{cov-ion}} & H_{\text{ion}} \end{pmatrix}$$

$H_{\text{cov-ion}} = H_{\text{ion-cov}}$ is the electronic coupling term between the ionic and covalent states and may be taken to represent that so called ionic-covalent resonance energy. In general, the diabatic state $\Phi_{\text{cov}}(r)$ and $\Phi_{\text{ion}}(r)$ are not mutually orthogonal [$\langle \Phi_{\text{cov}} | \Phi_{\text{ion}} \rangle = s(r)$ say]. Since s has r -dependence, we would prefer to represent H in a Schmidt orthogonalised basis :

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi'_{\text{cov}}(r) &= \Phi_{\text{cov}}(r) \\ \Phi'_{\text{ion}}(r) &= (1 - s^2)^{-1/2} \{ \Phi_{\text{ion}}(r) - s \Phi_{\text{cov}}(r) \} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

It may be noted that even after Schmidt transformation $\Phi'_{\text{cov}}(r)$ remains purely covalent while the covalent character introduced in Φ'_{ion} approximately goes as $s^2(r)$. Since $s^2(r)$ is a very small quantity $\Phi'_{\text{ion}}(r)$ remains virtually completely ionic except at very short distances which is not the region of our interest. The electronic coupling term is also affected by the transformation ;

$$H'_{\text{ion-cov}} = (1 - s^2)^{-1/2} [H_{\text{ion-cov}} - s^2 H_{\text{cov-ion}}]$$

Diagonalization of H' at various values of r , therefore, generates both adiabatic ground state and an excited state potential energy curve of AB molecule. The ground state energy so obtained together with the known values of $\langle H'_{\text{cov}} \rangle$ and $\langle H'_{\text{ion}} \rangle$ can be used to generate the electronegativity difference $\Delta\chi$ as a function of r . The procedure outlined in the two preceding sections can no doubt be actually implemented within the framework of molecular orbital theory. However, an apparently more roundabout way of achieving the same objective seems to work better. It involves direct calculations of constrained one-electron density matrices P_0 and P_+ for the covalent and ionic states, respectively. The route to P_0 and P_+ is chosen to be constrained variational as described in the section that follows.

Constrained variational route to P_0 and P_+ :

We start by considering a $2n$ – electron closed – shell

heteronuclear diatomic molecule AB. Let P_0 and P_+ represent the one-electron density matrices for the purely covalent and ionic forms of AB, respectively, in an N -dimensional discrete orthonormal basis (χ_p). In order to be N -representable, P_0 and P_+ must each satisfy the following constraints :

$$\begin{aligned} P_0^2 &= P_0, & P_0^\dagger &= P_0, & P_+^2 &= P_+, & P_+^\dagger &= P_+ \\ 2 \text{Tr} P_0 &= 2n, & & & 2 \text{Tr} P_+ &= 2n \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Since P_0 corresponds to the perfectly covalent structure, and P_+ to the perfectly ionic one we have the additional constraints that

$$2\text{Tr}(P_0 A_k) = a_k^0, \quad 2\text{Tr}(P_+ A_k) = a_k^\dagger \quad (16)$$

where a_k^0 and a_k^\dagger are the theoretically expected values of the property represented by A_k for the covalent and the ionic structures, respectively. The constrained determination of $P(P_0$ or $P_+)$ can be done in a number of ways. A convenient means of handling the problem involves minimizing the following penalised functionals^{9,10},

$$\begin{aligned} F(E, E_l, \sigma, \lambda, P_0) &= (E - E_l)^2 + \sigma \text{Tr} (P_0^2 - P_0)^2 \\ &+ \lambda_k [2\text{Tr}(P_0 A_k) - a_k^0] \quad (\text{for } P_0) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} F(E, E_l, \sigma, \lambda, P_+) &= (E - E_l)^2 + \sigma \text{Tr} (P_+^2 - P_+)^2 \\ &+ \lambda_r [2\text{Tr}(P_+ A_r) - a_r^\dagger] \quad (\text{for } P_+) \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

In eqns. (17) and (18), σ is a penalty weight factor of appropriate magnitude and dimension, λ_k is the Lagrangian multiplier for the K^{th} property constraint for the purely covalent or purely ionic states, respectively. Minimisation of F ($\delta F = 0$) then leads to the following equation for the iterative determination of P_0 or P_+ :

$$\begin{aligned} P_{i+1} &= 3 P_i^2 - 2 P_i^3 - \alpha (E_L - E_i) F_i - \gamma_i A_k, \\ &(P \equiv P_0 \text{ or } P_+) \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where,

$\alpha = 2 / \sigma$, $\gamma_i = \lambda_i / \sigma$, $F_i = G(P_i) + h$, $G(P_i) = 2J(P_i) - K(P_i)$ F is the appropriate Hartree-Fock matrix described by the two – electron interaction matrix $G(P)$. $J(P)$ and $K(P)$ are the Coulomb and exchange components of G respectively. The Lagrange multiplier γ_i at the i^{th} iteration is determined from the constraint condition $2\text{Tr}(P A_k) = a_k^0$ or a_r^\dagger by following the procedure described elsewhere (8).

Numerical implementation :

We demonstrate the viability of the proposed scheme with a model 2 – centre, 2 – electron problem, for example, the lithium-hydride molecule in the frozen core approximation. For the perfectly covalent form of Li-H, the

variationally stable one-electron density matrix satisfies the constraint¹¹,

$$\Delta q_c R_{\text{Li-H}} = \langle \mu_0 \rangle = 0 \quad (20)$$

while the ionic form is consistent with the constraint

$$\Delta q_c R_{\text{Li-H}} = \langle \mu_+ \rangle \quad (21)$$

where $\langle \mu_+ \rangle$ is the dipole moment of lithium hydride molecule due to the separation of one unit of charge over the distance $R_{\text{Li-H}}$ ($\Delta q_e = 1$). The former yields energy of the purely covalent form $E_0(R)$ while the latter yields the fully ionic counterpart $E_+(R)$. The actual calculations were carried out under the ZDO approximation to reduce the computational cost. We note, however, that it turned out to be quite difficult to satisfy the constraints fully at each R in one go. We could bypass the problem by adopting the following strategies. For computing $E_0(R)$, we have done a series of constrained variational calculations of P_0 at each R for small values of Δq_e (0.01, 0.001, 0.0001, etc.) and estimated ${}_{\text{Lt}} E_0(R)$ by forming the

$$\Delta q_e \rightarrow 0$$

diagonal Pade Approximant and then extrapolating to $\Delta q_e = 0$. Similarly, $E_+(R)$ has been calculated at each R by performing a series of constrained calculation of P_+ (hence, E_+) by using a series of values for Δq_e in the neighborhood of 1 (i.e. 0.9, 0.99, 0.999 etc.) and then estimating ${}_{\text{Lt}} E_+(R)$ by extrapolation

$$\Delta q_e \rightarrow 1$$

through diagonal Pade Approximant. The extrapolated values of $E_0(R)$ and $E_+(R)$ lead to the potential energy curves for the purely covalent and purely ionic forms of Li-H, respectively, which are displayed in Figs. 1(a) and 1(b). In the same figure, 1(c) represents the PE curve [$E(R)$] of the actual Li-H molecule (without any property constraint). We may now assume that the PE-curve 1(c) of the real molecule has been generated by interaction between the curves 1(a) and 1(b) and the interaction energy V is what Pauling's description refers to as the ionic-covalent interaction term of the energy matrix. A linear variation calculation including the ionic-covalent term then leads to the following secular equation (neglecting small overall between Ψ_0 and Ψ_+)

$$\begin{pmatrix} E_0(R) - \epsilon & V(R) \\ V(R) & E_+(R) - \epsilon \end{pmatrix}$$

The lower of the two roots of this secular equation ($E_g(R)$) is given by

$$\epsilon_g(R) = 1/2 \{E_0(R) + E_+(R)\} - [\{E_0(R) - E_+(R)\}^2 + 4V^2]^{1/2} \quad (23)$$

A little rearrangement immediately identifies V as a function of $E_g(R)$, $E_0(R)$ and $E_+(R)$,

$$V(R) = 1/2 [2 \epsilon_g(R) - \{E_0(R) + E_+(R)\}]_2 - \{E_0(R) - E_+(R)\}^2]^{1/2} \quad (24)$$

Fig. 1. Potential energy curves for the (a) perfectly covalent (b) perfectly ionic and (c) unconstrained form of lithium hydride molecule.

If we identify $\epsilon_g(R)$ with a theoretically computed accurate PE-curve of the diatom, eqn. (24) provides us with an explicit means of theoretically computing the ionic-covalent interaction energy provided we have already computed the PE curves for the perfectly ionic [$E_+(R)$] and perfectly covalent [$E_0(R)$] forms by the constrained variational procedure outlined in the previous section. Table 1. reports

Table 1. Computed values of ion-covalent interaction energy for Li-H at different internuclear separations together with the energy difference between the purely covalent (E_0) and ionic forms (E_+) of the molecule

R a.u.	$ E_0 - E_+ $ a.u.	$ \epsilon_g - (E_0 + E_+)/2 $ a.u.	$V_{\text{ion-corr}}$ eV
2.0	0.3748	0.2112	2.65
2.5	0.3436	0.1957	2.62
3.0	0.3297	0.1899	2.56
3.5	0.3053	0.1752	2.35
4.0	0.2536	0.1761	3.32
4.5	0.2160	0.1774	3.83

* Absolute values of the ground state energy of Li-H with respect to the mean energy of the covalent and ionic forms.

computed energy differences between the perfectly covalent and perfectly ionic forms of Li-H molecule at a number of the inter-nuclear distances. The difference between the energies of the actual Li-H molecule and the arithmetic mean of $E_0(R)$ and $E_+(R)$ and the ionic – covalent interaction energy $V(R)$ as predicted by us are also included. From the Table it is easily noted that both $V(R)$ and $E_g(R) - 1/2 [E_0(R) + E_+(R)]$ pass through minima as functions of R while $|E_0(R) - E_+(R)|$ decreases monotonically as R increases. The latter behaviour is quite expected, as in the dissociation limit $E_0(R)$ and $E_+(R)$ tend to be degenerate.

To compute the difference between electronegativities of Li and H atom $\Delta\chi = |\chi_{Li} - \chi_H|$, we may now invoke Pauling's prescription and assume that $\Delta\chi$ is directly proportional to the square-root of the extra stabilization (Δ) a measure of which is provided by the quantity $|E_g - E_0|$ in the present model. Computed values of Δ , $\Delta^{1/2}$ and $\Delta\chi = K\Delta^{1/2}$ (in eV) with $K = (27.23)^{1/2}$ are recorded in Table 2 for six different values of internuclear distance (R)

Table 2. Computed values of the difference of ground state electronegativities of Li and H atoms in the lithium hydride molecule at different internuclear separations

R a u	$\Delta = (E_g - E_0)^*$ a u	$\Delta^{1/2}$ (a u) ^{1/2}	$\Delta\chi = k_{1/2}\Delta^{1/2}$ eV
2.0	0.0238	0.1543	0.804
2.5	0.0242	0.1556	0.811
3.0	0.0250	0.1581	0.825
3.5	0.0240	0.1500	0.808
4.0	0.0275	0.1658	0.865
4.5	0.0287	0.1694	0.883

* E_g = Gr state energy of the actual LiH molecule at the given value of R . E_0 = Gr state energy of the perfectly covalent form at the same value of R .

$k = (27.23)$

A notable feature of our computed Pauling-like electronegativity difference is its R -independence. In fact, computed $\Delta\chi$ values for Li-H pass through a well defined minimum around the equilibrium internuclear separation. This feature is remarkable as it suggests a tendency of the hetero atom pair to equalise their electronegativities as much as possible

during molecule formation¹²⁻¹⁴

conclusion

We have shown how one can combine the ideas of constrained variational theory and the theory of effective Hamiltonians to give precise calculational procedures for computing the potential energy curves for the purely ionic and covalent forms of a heterodiatom, and then proceed to calculate what may be called Pauling's electronegativity difference. This difference depends upon the internuclear separation between the two atoms and lends to attain a minimum at the equilibrium geometry. We may then say that Pauling's scale has been theoretically rationalised.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to our colleagues for many useful discussions.

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